

THE INTERSECTION OF INSECURITY AND SUBSTANCE ABUSE IN NIGERIA: A CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS

Chinwe Onyemaechi, Anthony Onwudiwe and Achebe Sunday

Department of Psychology, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam.

Correspondence authors: ifeachoc@gmail.com, somadinaonwudiwe@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14860183>

Abstract: Nigeria faces a critical dual crisis of insecurity and substance abuse, which threatens both national stability and public health and undermines national development. This paper provides a conceptual analysis exploring the intersection of these two pressing issues, using Strain Theory to understand how societal pressures such as violence, economic instability, and displacement drive individuals toward substance abuse. The analysis examines the state of insecurity in Nigeria, focusing on insurgency, banditry. It also highlights how these create significant psychological trauma and mental health issues. The analysis also explores alarming rates of substance abuse in Nigeria which far exceed the global average and reveals that substance abuse and insecurity have a vicious cyclical relationship, where insecurity drives substance use, and widespread substance abuse worsens insecurity. This paper emphasizes the need for sustainable solutions that address the root causes of insecurity, the mental health crisis, and the socioeconomic factors driving both insecurity and drug use. It concludes with recommendations that strengthened security measures, expanded access to mental health and substance abuse treatment will go a long way in addressing these issues.

Keywords: Insecurity, Substance Abuse, Nigeria, Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The 16th goal of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), established in 2015, is "Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions." This goal emphasizes that everyone, regardless of their background, should live free from violence. Unfortunately, Nigeria has made little progress toward achieving this goal, as widespread insecurity continues to threaten peaceful coexistence in the country. Various forms of violence, including kidnapping, armed robbery, attacks by cattle herders, and other criminal activities, have victimized people across different levels of society (Efeurhobo & Egbon, 2023). Nigeria, unfortunately, has gained the unwanted reputation of being a country plagued by insecurity, with reports of violence and unrest emerging from every region (Ezeokana, et.al, 2017),

At the forefront of these security challenges is the Boko Haram insurgency and its splinter group, the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP). The Western media did not hold anything back when reporting the menace of Boko Haram, portraying the group as if they had captured all regions of Nigeria. While it is true that Boko Haram has caused, and continues to cause significant suffering in Nigeria, their activities have been concentrated in the northeastern region. Since 2009, these groups have waged a violent campaign targeting civilians, government forces, and infrastructure in the northeastern region of the country. Tactics such as bombings and

mass kidnappings, including the notorious abduction of the Chibok schoolgirls, have left a lasting impact on the region.

However, Boko Haram is not the only source of insecurity in Nigeria. The country faces threats from numerous non-state actors beyond the Boko Haram militia. In the North West and North Central regions, criminal gangs have capitalized on mass kidnappings, raiding villages, stealing livestock, and abducting people, including schoolchildren, for ransom. Banditry and kidnapping have become profitable enterprises, fueling instability and deepening the insecurity in these regions. The Middle Belt is plagued by frequent clashes between farmers and cattle herders, driven by competition over dwindling arable land and water. These conflicts often turn violent, leading to devastating losses of life and property. In the South East, separatist movements have sparked tensions and clashes with government forces, while the militants protest the unequal distribution of oil wealth and environmental degradation by vandalizing oil pipelines and engaging in piracy. Across all regions, factors such as armed robbery and drug trafficking, fueled by unemployment and poverty, contribute to the nation's pervasive insecurity. Businesses have shuttered, farmers cannot access their fields, in some region's churches are unable to hold services, and students attend school under constant fear of kidnappings (Onyemaechi, 2025; Achebe & Onyemaechi, 2023). These security challenges threaten Nigeria's national stability and the safety of its citizens.

In addition to these challenges, Nigeria is grappling with a growing substance use disorder (SUD) crisis. The 2016 global prevalence of drug use was reported to be 5.5% among individuals aged 15-64, according to the World Drug Report (Chaouali et al., 2021). Alarmingly, a 2018 report from the United Nations Office on Drug and Crime indicated that 14.4%, or 14.3 million people in the same age group in Nigeria, are drug users. This figure far exceeds the global average. Compounding this issue is the projection of a 130% increase in the prevalence of SUDs in sub-Saharan Africa by 2050 (Jaguga & Kwobah, 2020). This is especially concerning given Nigeria's current challenges with treatment and prevention systems. The rising prevalence of SUDs, as highlighted by Rotimi et al. (2022), represents a major public health challenge, underscoring the urgent need for comprehensive intervention strategies. Given the escalating rates of drug use, the development of robust treatment and prevention systems to combat the growing threat of substance abuse and its societal impact.

Purpose of the Paper

This paper aims to explore the connection between insecurity and substance abuse in Nigeria. This is achieved by analyzing how these two issues intersect and worsen each other. By examining the social, economic, and psychological dimensions of insecurity, as well as its contribution to rising rates of substance abuse, this paper seeks to highlight broader implications for public health, mental health, and national development. The analysis provides insights into how insecurity fosters conditions that lead to increased substance use, while substance abuse, in turn, perpetuates cycles of violence, instability, and poor mental health outcomes. This exploration is crucial for shaping effective policies and interventions that simultaneously address both challenges, ensuring Nigeria's long-term social and economic stability.

Insecurity and substance abuse are intertwined. This link creates a vicious cycle that works against both individual and societal well-being in Nigeria. This relationship not only undermines both public health and mental health but also poses significant threats to national development, as communities grappling with insecurity are more vulnerable to substance abuse, which further perpetuates instability and social disorder (Onyemaechi, et.al 2017 Anazonwu, et.ai, 2016, Achebe, 2023).

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To explore the intricate relationship between insecurity and substance abuse in Nigeria, it seems appropriate to apply Strain Theory as a framework. Developed by sociologist Robert K. Merton in 1938, this theory posits that societal pressures and cultural expectations can lead to when individuals are unable to achieve socially approved goals through legitimate means (Chism & Steinmetz, 2017). These goals might include economic success, family stability, or social status, but societal barriers like poverty, unemployment, or violence often hinder individuals from attaining them. When legitimate paths to success are blocked, individuals experience frustration and strain, which can push them toward deviant coping mechanisms, such as substance abuse.

In Nigeria, insecurity from insurgencies (e.g., Boko Haram), banditry, kidnappings, and economic. People in conflict zones like Borno State or Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra State are frequently exposed to trauma, displacement, and the breakdown of social structures. The psychological and emotional strain they experience makes them more vulnerable to substance abuse as a means of coping with the pervasive fear, anxiety, and despair in their lives. Substance use may offer temporary relief from the harshness of their realities, though it is often a maladaptive response to the larger systemic issues they face (Okonkwo, et.al, 2023).

Strain Theory highlights the cyclical relationship between insecurity and substance abuse. Violence and instability create conditions conducive to drug use, which in turn worsens the security situation the drug trade. By framing this analysis within Strain Theory, the paper emphasizes the socio-psychological mechanisms driving substance abuse in conflict-affected areas and highlights the necessity of addressing these strains to break the cycle of insecurity and drug use.

III. THE STATE OF INSECURITY IN NIGERIA

Nigeria is plagued by different types and levels of insecurity. From the Boko Haram terror in the Northeast to the conflict between the herdsmen and the farmers in the Middle Belt to the kidnappings in the South. Higazi (2016) discusses conflict and insecurity in the Jos Plateau region of north-central Nigeria, noting the clashes between Muslims and Christians as well as farmers and pastoralists in some northern areas. A Human Rights Watch report was cited in Okpaga et al. (2012) stating that about 935 people had been killed since 2009 due to violence from the Boko Haram group. It describes this as creating a "state of fear and insecurity" in Nigeria, particularly in the northern regions (Okpaga et al., 2012). the current state of insecurity far overshadows the report cited by Okpaga et al. (2012).

A look at the economic impact of insecurity in Nigeria proves this to be true as insecurity significantly affects various sectors and aspects of the economy. For instance, conflict-driven food insecurity has been observed to materialize through agricultural input and income shocks. An increase in conflict intensity, measured by the number of fatalities, leads to households relying on less preferred foods, limiting food variety, and reducing meal portion sizes (George et al., 2019). This suggests that the state of insecurity has worsened since 2012. It also makes a direct link between insecurity and reduced agricultural output, as well as decreased food availability and quality for affected households. The impact of insecurity on agricultural commercialization is also evident, with about 13% of cassava farm households not participating in the marketing of their produce (Otekunrin, 2022, Onyemaechi, 2025). This indicates a reduction in agricultural output and market participation, likely due to insecurity-related challenges. Conflict, along with drought and locusts, has been identified as a leading concern for African food security. The rise in food insecurity across sub-Saharan Africa since 2014 is largely attributable

to an increase in violent conflict, particularly in Nigeria and South Sudan (Anderson et al., 2021). This underscores the significant economic cost of conflict in terms of food security and agricultural productivity.

Types of Insecurity

1. **Insurgency:** Extremist groups like Boko Haram and the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP) have significantly contributed to insecurity in Nigeria, especially in the Northeastern region. Boko Haram, established in 2002, seeks to establish an Islamic state through violent means such as bombings, abductions, and attacks on civilians. As a splinter group of Boko Haram, ISWAP formed in 2016, focuses on targeting military and government institutions a caliphate in West Africa. Both groups recruit and radicalize youth, creating an environment of fear and instability. The prolonged insurgency has led to widespread displacement, economic collapse, and the destruction of social infrastructures. The resulting psychological trauma among Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) often drives individuals toward substance abuse as a coping mechanism. Poor living conditions in IDP camps, coupled with a lack of mental health support, create a cycle where victims of insurgency turn to drugs and some, in turn, may commit crimes or join insurgent groups to sustain their substance use.

2. **Banditry and Kidnappings:** Armed bandits frequently attack rural villages, stealing livestock, looting homes, and kidnapping people for ransom. Kidnappings have become widespread across Nigeria, affecting students, and even religious leaders. The anxiety and trauma experienced by families of kidnap victims can lead to substance abuse as they struggle to cope with the psychological impact. Additionally, some kidnapping victims themselves may turn to drugs after enduring the traumatic experience. Criminal gangs involved in banditry and kidnapping often abuse substances such as marijuana and cocaine, using them to gain. Others commit crimes to fund their drug habits, which further highlights the cyclical relationship between substance abuse and insecurity.

3. **Economic Insecurity (Unemployment, Poverty):** High unemployment, especially among youth, and widespread poverty are major sources of insecurity in Nigeria. The lack of job opportunities leaves many people unable to meet their basic needs, leading to feelings of frustration and hopelessness. In response, many individuals turn to substances like alcohol and drugs as a means of escaping their harsh realities. The link between economic hardship and substance abuse deepens the cycle of poverty and insecurity, as individuals engaging in substance use may become less productive, and others may resort to criminal activities to sustain their drug habits (Onyemaechi, et.al,2022, 2025). The absence of social safety nets and affordable healthcare systems worsens the problem, as those suffering from substance use disorders often cannot afford treatment, further entrenching the cycle of insecurity.

Consequences of Insecurity: Focus on Trauma and Mental Health

Insecurity in any state brings several far-reaching consequences, including displacement, family breakdown, and economic hardship (Eke-Okocha & Eze, 2023; George & Adelaja, 2022; Lee et al., 2022). However, this paper focuses exclusively on trauma and its impact on mental health. It is important to note that while trauma is not the sole consequence of insecurity, it is the particular focus of this discussion.

Insecurity, especially in the form of armed conflicts, banditry, insurgencies, and kidnappings, often results in large-scale displacement. Millions of Nigerians have been forced to abandon their homes, farmlands, and businesses, leaving behind livelihoods and social networks (Oyelade, 2008, Abamara et.al 2015). The displacement itself is traumatic, as individuals and families must flee their homes and communities to escape imminent danger. Many are forced to live in overcrowded camps, typically lacking necessities like food, clean

water, and healthcare. This displacement leads to prolonged psychological trauma as displaced people face not only the loss of their homes but also ongoing threats of violence and economic insecurity.

People often neglect the mental health toll of insecurity not minding its severity. Continuous exposure to violence and displacement heightens stress levels, increases the risk of anxiety and depression and in many cases, leads to the development of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Research has consistently shown a strong link between exposure to violence and the onset of mental health issues, particularly PTSD, depression, and anxiety (O'Connor & Seager, 2021; Wagner et al., 2020). These psychological impacts are compounded by the disruption of family structures, which play a central role in Nigerian society. Displacement often causes families to separate, weakening their ability to provide emotional support, guidance, and resilience in times of crisis (Osofsky & Osofsky, 2018, Aroyewun, 2014).

As family systems disintegrate, social cohesion within communities deteriorates, making individuals more vulnerable to both mental health disorders and substance abuse. This is particularly concerning for children, who may grow up without the stability and protection essential for healthy development, increasing their likelihood of trauma and emotional instability (Umeweke, et al. 2017). Displaced individuals, already burdened by the weight of their experiences, often lack access to adequate mental health care. Insecurity-affected areas tend to have underfunded healthcare systems, leaving those most in need of mental health support without access to necessary treatments or interventions.

The breakdown of family systems due to insecurity significantly worsens the psychological toll on individuals, as families often serve as primary sources of emotional support and resilience. Research highlights the role of family in adverse conditions. For example, family motivation has been shown to enhance individuals' commitment to their responsibilities and improve coping mechanisms in challenging environments (Onwudiwe & Nwokolo, 2024). Strengthening family structures, therefore, is a crucial buffer against the mental health challenges and substance abuses that insecurity often triggers.

IV. SUBSTANCE ABUSE IN NIGERIA: TRENDS AND PATTERNS

Evidence in the literature reveals that substance abuse in Nigeria is a significant public health concern, affecting various parts of society. Alcohol, long regarded as a social drug in some regions, is deeply integrated into Nigerian culture. Traditional and modern alcoholic beverages such as palm wine, burukutu, and beer are central to social events like weddings, funerals, and chieftaincy ceremonies (Obot, 2000; Okezie, 2020). However, the patterns of alcohol consumption have been evolving, with many now combining it with other substances. Okezie (2020) explores the cultural significance of alcohol in Nigeria, noting that it is consumed by people across different age groups, from young adults to the elderly, both with and without other drugs.

Substance abuse among youth is particularly concerning. Olanrewaju (2022) reports a high prevalence of substance abuse among students in southwestern Nigerian universities, where 45.7% of students are involved in drug use. The most commonly abused substances include codeine-based syrups, tramadol, alcohol, and cigarettes. In the Ejigbo community of Osun State, 12.3% of youths reportedly abuse substances, with shisha, tramadol, and alcohol being the most commonly used (Ajibola et al., 2023). A study by Adesanya et al. (1997) revealed that 6.6% of Nigerian prison inmates use cannabis, with 42.3% meeting the criteria for dependence. Furthermore, research on secondary school students in the Awka Educational Zone of Anambra State found a significant association between school type and crystal methamphetamine use (Uzor et al., 2023). These studies highlight

the widespread and serious nature of substance abuse in Nigeria, impacting different segments of the population and posing economic, social, and health-related challenges.

Substance abuse has far-reaching consequences, not only for the individuals involved but also for their families, communities, and society at large. For individuals, substance use significantly increases the risk of developing mental health disorders such as depression (Davis et al., 2008; Soltan et al., 2013), anxiety (Sultan et al., 2024), and psychosis (Baldaçara et al., 2023). It is also associated with physical health issues like cardiovascular diseases (Ciccirillo et al., 2022) and liver damage (Davis & Zhu, 2022), and can lead to cognitive impairment (Melugin et al., 2020) and suicidal ideation (López-Goñi et al., 2018), Ejidike, et.al 2023).

For families, substance abuse often results in dysfunction and breakdown, affecting relationships and stability within the household (Dawes et al., 1999). At the community level, the ripple effects are equally concerning. Substance abuse correlates with higher crime rates (Fazel, 2009; Andrews, 2012) and an increase in violence, both of which detract from community productivity (Amin et al., 2023) and exacerbate unemployment. These negative impacts place significant strain on social systems and contribute to economic instability.

Commonly Abused Substances

A discussion on the commonly abused substances will involve a wide range of legal and illegal drugs that can have significant impacts on physical and mental health. A brief examination of these commonly abused drugs is crucial at this stage.

1. Alcohol

Alcohol is widely accessible and socially sanctioned in many cultures including Nigeria (Okezie, 2020). It is one of the most commonly abused substances in Nigeria. In a study of undergraduates from four southwestern Nigerian universities, alcohol was found to be the most abused substance at 61.5% prevalence (Olanrewaju et al., 2022). Similarly, a survey of college students in Abeokuta, Ogun State revealed alcohol as having the highest lifetime prevalence rate at 34.3% (Umukoro et al., 2016). Its widespread availability and cultural acceptance contribute to its frequent use across various demographics. It is classified as a central nervous system depressant that impairs cognitive function and motor coordination. While moderate alcohol consumption is socially accepted in many communities, excessive consumption has become a serious issue, particularly among young people. Alcohol abuse often serves as a coping mechanism for individuals dealing with economic hardship, unemployment, or emotional stress brought on by insecurity and violence (Olanrewaju et al., 2022). Acute effects include reduced inhibitions, impaired judgment, and slowed reflexes. Prolonged misuse may result in dependency, liver disease, cardiovascular problems, and neurological damage (Davidson et al., 2023; Provan & Forrest, 2023). Withdrawal symptoms can be severe and potentially life-threatening. Alcohol use disorder affects millions globally and is a leading cause of preventable death.

2. Cannabis

Cannabis, known locally as "weed" or "ganja," is another widely abused substance in Nigeria (UNODC, 2018; Omatseye, 2017). Cannabis produces psychoactive effects primarily attributed to the delta-9-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) compound (Razmara et al., 2023; Tadayoni et al., 2020). It is commonly used by young adults, especially in urban areas, to escape from the pressures of economic and social challenges. The cultivation and trafficking of cannabis have also become significant issues in Nigeria, the drug within West Africa (Abikoye et al., 2020, Aroyewun, et.al 2014). Consumption methods include inhalation (smoking or

vaporizing), ingesting edible products, and topical applications. Short-term effects may include altered perception, impaired memory, and increased appetite. Potential for psychological dependence exists, particularly with frequent, heavy use. Regular cannabis use has been linked to mental health disorders such as psychosis, anxiety, and depression, and it often co-occurs with other substance use disorders (Lev-Ran et al., 2012; Zaman et al., 2015). Despite being illegal, cannabis remains readily available, contributing to both personal and societal challenges, particularly in communities already grappling with insecurity.

3. Prescription Drugs

The misuse of prescription drugs, especially opioids like tramadol and codeine, has become a growing problem in Nigeria. Tramadol, a pain reliever, and codeine, an ingredient in cough syrups, are frequently abused for their euphoric effects (UNODC, 2018; Omatseye, 2017). Tramadol is an opioid analgesic associated with risk of physical dependence and withdrawal symptoms (Sams & Cheng, 2023). Codeine is an opioid utilized for pain management and cough suppression. Benzodiazepines are prescribed for anxiety, insomnia, and seizure disorders. These drugs are often misused by young people, who may be drawn to them as a means of escaping psychological stress, trauma, or the difficulties of daily life. The easy accessibility of these medications, despite regulatory efforts, has contributed to widespread abuse, leading to addiction, overdose, and severe health complications, including respiratory depression and organ damage.

4. Illicit substances

Many people use many illicit drugs, but this paper will focus on crystal methamphetamine which is highly abused in Nigeria. This substance has become a significant concern in Nigeria, particularly in the Southeast region (Nnaemedo et al., 2023). Crystal meth produces stimulant effects, including increased energy and alertness, intense euphoria, and appetite suppression through its actions on dopaminergic, serotonergic, and adrenergic systems (Mckelvie & Gercek, 2017). However, its use can lead to serious health effects, including infertility, cancer, and DNA damage, especially among long-term users (Singwane & Ramoshaba, 2023 Okonkwo et.al, 2023).

V. THE INTERSECTION OF INSECURITY AND SUBSTANCE ABUSE

Strain Theory posits that when people cannot achieve socially approved goals through legitimate means, they experience strain, leading to deviant behaviours like substance abuse. In Nigeria, various forms of insecurity create significant strains that push individuals towards drug use. For example, insecurity from the Boko Haram insurgency, banditry, and farmer-herder clashes leads to mass displacement, resulting in a lack of resources and a disruption to normal life for many people. Displaced individuals, struggling with poor living conditions and limited access to necessities, may turn to substance abuse as a maladaptive coping mechanism to escape their harsh realities. Economic insecurity and unemployment also contribute to strain, preventing individuals from achieving financial success, leading to feelings of frustration, hopelessness and an increased risk of substance abuse. Additionally, exposure to violence and trauma, such as kidnappings and attacks, psychological trauma and chronic stress, to seek temporary relief through drugs and alcohol. Finally, the breakdown of social structures and the loss of social support networks due to displacement and insecurity can increase feelings of isolation and vulnerability, making people more prone to substance abuse. These strains, caused by the various forms of insecurity, create a cycle of vulnerability and contribute to the prevalence of substance abuse in Nigeria.

Insecurity as a Driver of Substance Abuse

In Nigeria, regions plagued by violence, kidnapping, economic instability, and insurgency, often have these issues of insecurity driving substance abuse. People grappling with the social, psychological, and economic impacts of this insecurity often turn to substances as a way to cope with the overwhelming trauma and stress. The relationship between substance abuse and insecurity, however, is complex and can be understood through several critical mechanisms: the psychological effects of trauma and violence, substance use as a coping strategy, and the role of displacement and lack of social support.

Nigeria has faced ongoing insecurity for decades. Less than a decade after gaining independence, the country was engulfed in a civil war, during which acts of genocide and atrocities were committed against the Igbo people (Afsai, 2016; Otiono, 2021; Daly, 2023). The trauma from the civil war still lingers, especially for the Igbo. Post-war, Nigeria has continued to battle widespread insecurity, with insurgent groups like Boko Haram and criminal gangs engaging in violence and kidnappings. These ongoing security challenges have significantly affected the mental health of the population, with many witnessing bombings, killings, and abductions, resulting in elevated levels of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Njoku & Nwachukwu, 2015; Omoroghomwan et al., 2018). The daily occurrence of violence has normalized fear, helplessness, and hopelessness, worsening the psychological toll on Nigerians. This psychological burden is compounded by the lack of adequate mental health services. In response, many people seek solace in harmful alternatives, with substance use becoming a prevalent coping mechanism.

The effects of insecurity are not limited to immediate trauma; they also cause long-term mental health problems. Chronic stress and fear lead to changes in brain chemistry and structure, increasing susceptibility to addiction and other mental health disorders (Suvrathan et al., 2014). Moreover, the state of constant hypervigilance required to survive in insecure environments exhausts individuals emotionally, further driving them towards substance use for temporary relief (Getzen, 2021).

In the absence of formal support systems, many individuals turn to drugs and alcohol for a fleeting escape from the emotional toll of insecurity. Substance abuse has become a tragic coping mechanism for those living under constant strain, with alcohol, cannabis, opioids like codeine, and tramadol often used to numb the emotional pain associated with insecurity (Torrens et al., 2014). While these substances may seem to offer temporary relief, they ultimately worsen the underlying trauma, leading to addiction and further mental and physical health deterioration (Honorato et al., 2016).

A further consequence of insecurity is mass displacement, which tears at the social fabric of communities. In Nigeria, millions have become internally displaced due to insecurity (Omoroghomwan et al., 2018; Tar & Ayegba, 2021). The Boko Haram conflict in the northeast has displaced over 2.1 million people, leaving 7 million in need of humanitarian assistance (Tar & Ayegba, 2021). Other sources of displacement include herdsman-farmer conflicts and communal violence (Akpehe et al., 2021; Alao et al., 2019). Displaced individuals often find themselves in camps with poor living conditions, lacking basic services like healthcare, clean water, and food. This, friends, and traditional support systems, are crucial during crises.

The loss of these support networks significantly worsens the emotional toll on displaced individuals, as the traditional family structure typically offers guidance, emotional support, and a sense of belonging. When this structure is fractured, people are left vulnerable, particularly young people, who face uncertain futures and limited opportunities for education and employment. In this context, young people are at heightened risk of substance

abuse, with IDP camps becoming hotspots for substance use due to the prevalent boredom, frustration, and trauma. The normalization of substance uses within these settings, especially among younger populations, further exacerbates the crisis. This breakdown of social cohesion extends beyond IDP camps into regions affected by insecurity, where addiction and mental health struggles hinder productivity and collective recovery.

It must be noted, however, that adverse growing-up experiences significantly influence mental resilience, shaping how individuals cope with adversity. Research shows that individuals with diminished mental resilience are more likely to turn to unhealthy coping mechanisms, including substance abuse, as a way to navigate the psychological toll of adverse experiences (Okwuogu & Onwudiwe, 2024; Okonkwo, et.al 20233. Insecurity then, which is marked by trauma and instability, further weakens the development of resilience, and this amplifies vulnerability to substance abuse. So, lack of resilience becomes a pathway from insecurity and substance abuse.

Substance Abuse Worsens Insecurity

Substance abuse not only worsens individual well-being but also plays a significant role in deepening insecurity through multiple interconnected mechanisms, particularly drug trafficking and the criminal networks it sustains. One of the primary ways this occurs is through the illicit drug trade, which fuels armed groups and criminal organizations, creating a vicious cycle of addiction, crime, and violence.

In Nigeria, the high rate of drug trafficking contributes directly to substance abuse while simultaneously strengthening the operations of criminal and insurgent groups. These groups often rely on the drug trade to fund their activities. Many organized crime syndicates and insurgent groups in Nigeria likely benefit from the profits of drug trafficking (Ajiboye, 2022). Although direct evidence of Boko Haram's involvement in the drug trade is limited, the growing demand for substances such as cannabis, tramadol, and codeine has resulted in a flourishing black market. This market is often controlled by organized crime syndicates, whose revenues help finance violent activities.

Competition for control over drug routes and markets has led to increased violence between rival criminal factions, resulting in gang warfare and territorial disputes. While drug trafficking is often associated with organized crime, there is evidence linking it to insurgent activities as well. In Nigeria, increasing attacks against oil transports may indicate efforts by insurgents to use piracy profits as an additional revenue stream to fund their campaigns against the government (Daxecker & Prins, 2017).

At the individual level, substance abuse impairs judgment, heightens aggression, and increases the likelihood of engaging in criminal activities such as theft, and assault. Individuals addicted to substances may resort to extreme measures, including kidnapping for ransom, to fund their drug habits. The rise in crimes driven by substance use worsens insecurity as addicts become both perpetrators and victims of violence. These acts of criminality disrupt community cohesion and contribute to a generalized sense of fear and mistrust.

This cycle is hard to break, as criminal activities funded by drug trafficking not only increase substance availability but also exacerbate insecurity. In regions with weak law enforcement and limited judicial capacity, criminal networks and insurgent groups thrive. The resulting instability leads to further lawlessness, creating a feedback loop in which insecurity and substance abuse mutually reinforce one another.

The rise in substance abuse also places a considerable burden on Nigeria's already strained justice and healthcare systems. As more individuals become involved in drug-related crimes, the judicial system becomes overwhelmed,

and the healthcare sector is forced to manage the physical and mental health consequences of addiction. The inability of these institutions to cope with the escalating crisis allows criminal networks to grow unchecked, making it even harder to combat both the drug trade and the insecurity it perpetuates.

In conclusion, substance abuse does not merely respond to insecurity but actively worsens it by fueling criminal networks and exacerbating violence. The drug trade becomes a lucrative source of funding for armed groups and criminal syndicates, further destabilizing regions. At the same time, individuals suffering from addiction may engage in crime to sustain their habits, further contributing to the cycle of violence and insecurity.

VI. SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Insecurity and substance abuse make up a double-headed monster, with each head of this monster being able to resuscitate the other head in the event of an attack on one head. This means that these intertwined issues of insecurity and substance abuse in Nigeria require a more comprehensive strategy that attends to both problems at the same time. Understanding this will help the critical stakeholders successfully plan strategies to defeat this monster. Any attack on one head without attacking the other equally will only lead to failure. This is because each can feed the other. If stakeholders like the government focus on insecurity without dealing with the substance abuse menace, they will eventually see the abuse menace reviving insecurity.

Strengthening Security measures

The first step to achieving this will be strengthening security measures in the areas involved. Effective security is the basis for addressing the broader problems of insecurity and substance abuse in Nigeria. Strengthening security encompasses bolstering the capacity of law enforcement by training them properly and equipping them appropriately to combat violence and criminal activities. These violent and criminal activities include banditry, kidnappings, and armed robbery. The stakeholders can do this by increasing funding, improving training, and providing modern equipment for security personnel. This also involves better coordination among security forces to address threats posed by the bandits and criminal gangs who kidnap and terrorize the citizens. Community policing has also been found to be effective in strengthening security in areas with heightened insecurity. It has positively impacted Anambra state, particularly through the Anambra Vigilante Services (Igwebuike et al., 2023, Onyemaechi, 2025s). By building safer environments, people are less likely to experience the trauma and stress that often contribute to mental health disorders and substance abuse. The ultimate goal of improved security is to create stable, peaceful communities where people can lead productive lives without constant fear.

Expanding Access to Mental Health Services

Plans must be made to expand mental health services, especially in conflict-affected regions and internally displaced persons (IDP) camps. This is because these areas have the greatest number of vulnerable persons, as many individuals in these areas have experienced significant trauma. Not minding the considerable trauma, mental health care is severely limited in these areas. Many individuals in these areas would like to be treated for substance use disorder, but unfortunately, they lack access to proper treatment facilities. Mental health professionals, which include trained psychiatrists, psychologists, and, should be deployed to these areas to provide immediate support and care. This can be done through the introduction of mobile clinics in areas with high rates of substance abuse and mental health issues. Mobile Mental Health Clinics (MMHCs) are emerging as an innovative solution to address the escalating mental health crisis, particularly in underserved communities. These clinics bring mental health services directly to patients' doorsteps, offering a proactive, cost-effective model combining cutting-edge

technology with streamlined patient care (Kukreja et al., 2023). This approach has proven effective in reaching diverse, underserved populations and providing essential health services (Maughan et al., 2024).

Implementing Community-Based Programs

Communities are. This shows how important it is to implement community-based programs to help rebuild the social networks and support systems eroded by insecurity. The first aim of these programs should be to rebuild traditional support systems. Families, communities, and religious structures play a significant role in Nigerian society (Adejoh et al., 2024, Okonkwo, et.al, 2023). To successfully achieve this, community leaders and religious figures could be trained to recognize the signs of substance abuse and to offer support or direct individuals to professional help. The critical role of social support in mental health has been the focus of different studies. Onyemaechi et al. (2024) found that mothers with low self-esteem and inadequate social support were more prone to experiencing postpartum depression. This highlights the importance of social networks and self-perception in maintaining psychological well-being, suggesting that a lack of social integration and poor self-appraisal can significantly contribute to mental distress (Onyemaechi et al., 2024). These findings reinforce the need for interventions that strengthen social support systems and enhance self-esteem to mitigate mental health challenges, particularly in vulnerable populations experiencing insecurity. Another key aim of these community-based programs would be promoting resilience and coping strategies. This could be achieved through workshops, support groups, and educational campaigns that are focused on promoting resilience and teaching individuals how to cope with stress, trauma, and uncertainty in adaptive ways.

Developing Targeted Substance Abuse Prevention and Treatment Programs

Individuals turn to substance abuse as a coping mechanism for trauma, stress, and displacement. This is general, especially in conflict-affected and insecure areas. For this reason, it becomes paramount that substance abuse prevention and treatment programs should be introduced in these communities to curb the growing rates of addiction. These programs should, among other things, incorporate trauma-informed care. They must recognize the deep psychological trauma that many individuals have experienced due to violence and displacement. These individuals, for lack of proper care and guidance, rush into substance abuse to cope with the trauma. So, these programs that aim to treat them should be holistic, addressing both the addiction and the underlying trauma through, psychotherapy, and support goals. It is also critical for stakeholders to engage in awareness campaigns. This is a way of educating the public on the evil or consequences of engaging in substance abuse. Prevention efforts must focus on education, teaching people about the risks of substance and offering alternatives for coping with trauma and stress. These campaigns can be delivered through schools, religious organizations, and media.

Addressing Socioeconomic Factors

Factors such as poverty and unemployment often worsen insecurity and substance abuse. They make people more vulnerable to both insecurity and substance abuse. Youth unemployment is closely linked to increased crime and substance use rates, as evidenced by several studies. Research shows that a shortage of attractive job opportunities is the principal source of long-term non-employment among youth, which can (Clark & Summers, 1978). The conclusions of the stated research can be extrapolated to the situation of youths in Nigeria. Many youths in Nigeria today are jobless, and they rush into crimes and substance use because they are not gainfully employed. Therefore, the government, NGOs, and private sector should invest in initiatives that provide employment opportunities, especially for youth in conflict-affected regions. Job placement services, entrepreneurship programs, and

vocational training could provide people with economic stability and, in turn, reduce their vulnerability to crime and substance abuse. Apart from job creation, social safety nets such as food assistance, unemployment benefits, and healthcare subsidies can also reduce the economic pressure that often drives people toward. To benefit most from these programs, they should target the most vulnerable populations, including displaced persons, single-parent households, and impoverished communities.

VII. CONCLUSION

The crises of insecurity and substance abuse are deeply interconnected. This creates a cycle that threatens the country's public health, stability, and development. Insurgency, banditry, and economic instability are all forms of insecurity experienced in Nigeria. They generate significant societal strain, which drives individuals toward substance abuse as a coping mechanism for trauma, frustration, fear, and anxiety. At the same time, the rising prevalence of substance abuse worsens insecurity by fuelling criminal activities. This analysis grounded in Strain Theory has demonstrated how the societal pressures caused by insecurity lead to substance abuse especially among vulnerable populations such as youth, displaced persons, and those living in poverty. The paper highlights the need for comprehensive, multi-angled approaches to break this cycle. Addressing the root cause of insecurity is critical to reducing the societal strain that drives substance abuse. Ultimately, addressing Nigeria's dual crises of insecurity and substance abuse requires sustained commitment from all sectors, including government, civil society, and international partners. By tackling both issues in tandem, Nigeria can move toward a future where its citizens can thrive in a secure and healthy environment.

REFERENCES

- Abikoye, G. E., Edewor, D. O., Sunday, D. B., Abayomi, O., Obot, I. S., & Nelson, E. Socioeconomic context of cannabis cultivation and trafficking in selected Nigerian communities (Vol. 62, Issue 1, pp. 9–26). (2020). united nations. <https://doi.org/10.18356/fa33b4cf-en>
- Achebe, S.C. & Onyemaechi, C.I. (2023). Moral Disengagement and Gender as predictors of tendency to commit crime among adolescents in Anambra State. *Ziks Journal of Research*, 6 (2).
- Adejoh, S. O., Adejoh, S. O., Odey, M. O., Oyelowo, O. T., Osazuwa, P., & Tade, T. (2024). Social capital in the management of breast cancer in Lagos, Nigeria. *Palliative & Supportive Care*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s147895152400049x>
- Adesanya, A., Ohaeri, J. U., Ogunlesi, A. O., Adamson, T. A., & Odejide, O. A. (1997). Psychoactive substance abuse among inmates of a Nigerian prison population. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*, 47(1), 39–44.
- Afsai, S. (2016). Nigeria's Igbo Jews: Jewish identity and practice in Abuja. *Anthropology Today*, 32(2), 14–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8322.12239>
- Ajibola, I., Oluwaseye, A., Oluwaseyi, O., Loliya, A., Omotolani, O., Ayomikun, O., Olumide, A., Ayodele Olatayo, A., Ebunoluwa, O., Anatasia, M., Jesulayomi, E., Gloria, E., Daniella, A., Victoria, A., Emmanuel, O., Blessing, A., & Ibukun Mary, A. (2023). Prevalence, pattern and determinants of

substance abuse among youths in a rural community of Osun State, Southwest Nigeria. *African Health Sciences*, 23(4), 563–574. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v23i4.59>

Ajiboye, B. M. (2022). Glomming to Gloom: The Raging Peril of Drug Abuse and Trafficking in Nigeria. *ACC Journal*, 28(3), 7–19. <https://doi.org/10.15240/tul/004/2022-3-001>

Akpehe, G. A., Mase, A. J., Dewua, E. R., & Timin, L. (2021). Communal Violence and the Extremity of Poverty among Rural Farmers in the North-Central Region of Nigeria. *European Journal of Social Sciences Studies*, 6(3). <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejsss.v6i3.1048>

Alao, D. O., Ogunwemimo, T., Alao, E. M., Shaibume, B., & Ogunwemimo, O. (2019). Herdsmen/Native Farmers' Violence in Benue State and Food Security in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(6). <https://doi.org/10.36941/mjss-2019-0077>

Amin, U., Amin, I., Jan, R., & Malla, A. M. (2023). Substance Abuse: A Public Health Concern. *Indian Journal of Psychiatric Nursing*, 20(2), 168–178. https://doi.org/10.4103/iopn.iopn_25_23

Ananzonwu, C. O., Onyemaechi, C. I. & Igwilo, C. (2016). Psychology of Kidnapping. *Practicum Psychologia* (6) 104-120.

Anderson, W., Taylor, C., Schlenker, W., De Sherbinin, A., Mendeloff, D., Seager, R., Markey, K., Mcdermid, S., Cottier, F., & Ilboudo-Nébié, E. (2021). Violent conflict exacerbated drought-related food insecurity between 2009 and 2019 in sub-Saharan Africa. *Nature Food*, 2(8), 603–615. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00327-4>

Andrews, D. (2012). Chapter 9 - Substance Abuse. In *The Psychology of Criminal Conduct* (pp. 275–295). . <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-1-4224-6329-1.50014-2>

Aroyewun, A.B., Adeyemo, O.S. & Ifeacho, C. I. (2014). Social- Demographic variables and personality profiles of patients with substance abuse disorder. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4 (15).

Baldaçara, L., Ramos, A., & Castaldelli-Maia, J. M. (2023). Managing drug-induced psychosis. In *International Review of Psychiatry: Vol. ahead-of-print* (Issue ahead-of-print, pp. 496–502). francis. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540261.2023.2261544>

Boettger, S., Bergman, M., Jenewein, J., & Boettger, S. (2014). Assessment of decisional capacity: Prevalence of medical illness and psychiatric comorbidities. *Palliative and Supportive Care*, 13(5), 1275–1281. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1478951514001266>

Chaouali, N., Amira, D., Salem, K. B., Hedhili, A., Salah, N. B., & Moslah, B. (2021). Illicit substances identified in the urine of 11.170 suspected drug users in North Tunisia. *The Pan African Medical Journal*, 38(2). <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2021.38.20.26781>

Chism, K. A., & Steinmetz, K. F. (2017). Technocrime and Strain Theory (pp. 66–84). . <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315117249-5>

Ciccirillo, F., Morici, N., Giallauria, F., Santucci, A., Caldarola, P., Cocozza, S., Boschini, A., Amico, A. F., Gulizia, M. M., Grosseto, D., Abrignani, M. G., Gabrielli, D., Gabriele, M., & Colivicchi, F. (2022). Substance abuse and cardiovascular risk: cocaine. *Giornale Italiano Di Cardiologia* (2006), 23(6), 444–453. <https://doi.org/10.1714/3810.37941>

Clark, K., & Summers, L. (1978). *The Dynamics of Youth Unemployment*. of economic research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w0274>

Daly, S. F. C. (2023). Secession and Genocide in the Republic of Biafra, 1966–1970 (pp. 476–496). university. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108767118.021>

Davidson, M., Hossain, M. K., Apostolopoulos, V., Nurgali, K., Rashidi, N., & Raza, A. (2023). Tryptophan and Substance Abuse: Mechanisms and Impact. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(3), 2737. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24032737>

Davis, L., Uezato, A., Frazier, E., & Newell, J. M. (2008). Major depression and comorbid substance use disorders. *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*, 21(1), 14–18. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ycp.0b013e3282f32408>

Davis, S., & Zhu, J. (2022). Substance abuse and neurotransmission. *Advances in Pharmacology* (San Diego, Calif.), 93, 403–441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.apha.2021.10.007>

Dawes, M. A., Dorn, L. D., Moss, H. B., Yao, J. K., Kirisci, L., Ammerman, R. T., & Tarter, R. E. (1999). boys at risk for substance abuse. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*, 55(1–2), 165–176. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0376-8716\(99\)00003-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0376-8716(99)00003-4)

Daxecker, U., & Prins, B. C. (2017). Financing rebellion. *Journal of Peace Research*, 54(2), 215–230. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022343316683436>

Efeurhobo & Egbon (2023). Insecurity in Nigeria: Its implications for the education sector. *Wukari International Studies Journal*, Vol 7 (3)

Ejidike, G. O & Onyemaechi, C. I. (2023). Harmony Restoration Therapy and Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy in an African Setting: A Comparative Analysis. *International Journal for Psychotherapy In Africa* 8 (1)

- Eke-Okocha, N. P., & Eze, C. G. (2023). Boko Haram Insurgency North-Eastern Nigeria, How Has This Influenced Food Insecurity in the Region? (pp. 89–102). *springer nature*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-7295-9_6
- Erah F, Omatseye A. (2017). Drug and alcohol abuse among secondary school students in a rural community in south-south Nigeria. *Ann Med and Surg Pract*. 2 (2), 85–91.
- Ezeokana, J.O., Onyemaechi, C. I. & Agu, R. (2017). Boko haram terrorism and haram phobia: The role of new media. *Nnadiabube Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(2) 38-51.
- Fazel, S. (2009). Schizophrenia, Substance Abuse, and Violent Crime. *JAMA*, 301(19). <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2009.675>
- George, J., & Adelaja, A. (2022). Armed conflicts, forced displacement and food security in host communities. *World Development*, 158, 105991. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2022.105991>
- George, J., Adelaja, A., & Weatherspoon, D. (2019). Armed Conflicts and Food Insecurity: Evidence from Boko Haram's Attacks. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 102(1), 114–131. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajae/aaz039>
- Getzen, S. (2021). Guarding Against Strain: The Moderating Role of Nonwork Experiences in the Relationship Between Work-Related Hypervigilance and Strain in Correctional Officers []. <https://doi.org/10.15760/etd.7678>
- Gundur, R. V. (2022). Violence (pp. 92–102). *university*. <https://doi.org/10.7591/cornell/9781501764462.003.0008>
- Gutierrez, S. E., & Van Puymbroeck, C. (2006). Childhood and adult violence in the lives of women who misuse substances. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 11(5), 497–513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2006.01.010>
- Higazi, A. (2016). Farmer-pastoralist conflicts on the Jos Plateau, central Nigeria: security responses of local vigilantes and the Nigerian state. *Conflict, Security & Development*, 16(4), 365–385. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14678802.2016.1200314>
- Honorato, B., Clough, A. R., & Caltabiano, N. (2016). From trauma to incarceration: exploring the trajectory in a qualitative study in male prison inmates from north Queensland, Australia. *Health & Justice*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40352-016-0034-x>
- Igwebuike, P., Unachukwu, V. U., Adama A. M., & Erunke, C. E. (2023). Local policing and its implication for security in Anambra State, Nigeria. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 18(2), 961–968. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.2.0917>

- Jaguga, F., Kwobah, E. (2020). A review of the public sector substance uses disorder treatment and prevention systems in Kenya. *Subst Abuse Treat Prev Policy* 15, 47. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13011-020-00291-5>
- Kukreja, P., Santra, S., & Saxena, K. (2023). Edition 62 – Mental Health Driving Change: Addressing America's Mental Health Crisis through the Power of Mobile Clinics in Underserved Communities. *HPHR Journal*, 62. <https://doi.org/10.54111/0001/jjj10>
- Lee, J. Y., Grogan-Kaylor, A. C., Lee, S. J., & Volling, B. L. (2022). Examining mechanisms linking economic insecurity to interparental conflict among couples with low income. *Family Relations*, 72(3), 1158–1185. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fare.12698>
- Lev-Ran, S., Le Foll, B., Mckenzie, K., & Rehm, J. (2012). Cannabis use and mental health-related quality of life among individuals with anxiety disorders. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 26(8), 799–810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2012.07.002>
- López-Goñi, J. J., Fernández-Montalvo, J., Arteaga, A., & Haro, B. (2018). Suicidal ideation and attempts in patients who seek treatment for substance use disorder. *Psychiatry Research*, 269, 542–548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2018.08.100>
- Lyman, M. (2012b). Chapter 9 - Foreign Drug-Trafficking Organizations. In *Drugs in Society* (pp. 285–321). . <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-1-4377-4450-7.00009-6>
- Maughan, E., Richardson, C., & Nazar, H. (2024). A cross-sectional investigation of a mobile health clinic run by undergraduate pharmacy students providing services to underserved communities. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-024-01783-1>
- Mckelvie, M. A., & Gercek, Y. (2017). Paralytic Ileus Secondary to Methamphetamine Abuse: A Rare Case. *Case Reports in Surgery*, 2017(13), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/9762803>
- Melugin, P. R., Siciliano, C. A., & Nolan, S. O. (2020). Bidirectional causality between addiction and cognitive deficits. *International Review of Neurobiology*, 157, 371–407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.irn.2020.11.001>
- Namadi MM. (2016). Drug abuse among adolescents in Kano metropolis, Nigeria. *IJASS*. 2 (1), 195–206. [10.11648/j.ajns.20170602.16](https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajns.20170602.16)
- Njoku, J. U., & Nwachukwu, J. (2015). The Effects of Boko Haram's Insecurity on Nigeria's Economy. *AFRREV IJAH: An International Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 4(3), 26–41. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ijah.v4i3.3>
- Nnaemedo, B., Nwaugo, V., & Nwoko, M. (2023). Church's Response to Methamphetamine (Mkpuru-Mmiri) Abuse among Young People in Southeast Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Humanities and Social Science*, 06(02), 132–144. <https://doi.org/10.54922/ijehss.2023.0505>

- O'Connor, K., & Seager, J. (2021). Displacement, Violence, and Mental Health: Evidence from Rohingya Adolescents in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(10), 5318. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18105318>
- Obot, I. S. (2000). The measurement of drinking patterns and alcohol problems in Nigeria. *Journal of Substance Abuse*, 12(1–2), 169–181.
- Okezie, P. (2020). The Rising Effect of Alcohol and Substance Abuse in Nigeria. SSRN.
- Okonkwo, C. O. Okonkwo, C. O, Onyemaechi, C.I, Okpaleke, U.V. & Nwankwo, E. A. (2023). Predictive Impact of Ego-Identity on Mkpuru Mmiri (Methamphetamine) Use Among Youths In Okpoko, Ogbaru Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal Of Psychology and Behavioural Disciplines*, Coou 2 (3)
- Okpaga, A., Eme, O. I., & Ugwu, S. C. (2012). Activities of Boko Haram and Insecurity Question in Nigeria. *Oman Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(9), 77–99. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0002163>
- Okwuogo, P. C., & Onwudiwe, A. O. (2024). Role of growing-up experiences on mental resilience and creative thinking of Nigerian youths. *Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Disciplines*, 4(1), 1–15.
- Olanrewaju, J. A., Enya, J. I., Olanrewaju, I., Owolabi, J. O., Osuoya, Q., Johnson, B. S., Feyisike Johnson, O., Hamzat, E. O., Udekwu, M. O., & Bamidele, R. (2022). An assessment of drug and substance abuse prevalence: a cross-sectional study among undergraduates in selected southwestern universities in Nigeria. *The Journal of International Medical Research*, 50(10), 030006052211300. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03000605221130039>
- Omoroghomwan, O., Isahya'U, U., & Bafeto, A. (2018). Politics, Insecurity and Internally Displaced Persons () in North-Eastern Nigeria, 2009-2015: A Critical Review. *Inquiry: Critical Thinking Across the Disciplines*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.21533/isjss.v3i1.101>
- Onwudiwe, A. O., & Nwokolo, E. E. (2024). Family Motivation and Pay Satisfaction as Predictors of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour among Non-Teaching Staff of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science*, 9(9), 665–673. <https://doi.org/10.51584/IJRIAS.2024.909059>
- Onyemaechi, C. I., Okere, E., Chukwuemeka, N. & Nnaemeka, I.J. (2017). Unemployment and Mental: Focus on Nigerian Youths. *Psychologia*, 7 (1).
- Onyemaechi, C., Aroyewun, B. A., & Ifeagwazi, C. M. (2017). Postpartum depression: The role of self-esteem, social support, and age. *IFE Psychologia*, 25(2).

Onyemaechi, C.I., Unadike, M, Izuchukwu, C. Onwusobalu, P & Umenweke, O., (2022). Internet Addiction and Its Psychological Wellbeing Correlate Among Undergraduates. *Journal of Psychology and Behavioural Disciplines*, Coou 2 (1).

Onyemaechi, C.I. (2025). Economic crises in Nigeria: A Psychological Perspective. *Ojukwu of Psychological Services*1(1)1-10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14764142>

Osofsky, J. D., & Osofsky, H. J. (2018). Challenges in building child and family resilience after disasters. *Journal of Family Social Work*, 21(2), 115–128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10522158.2018.1427644>

Otekunrin, O. A. (2022). Investigating food insecurity, health and environment-related factors, and agricultural commercialization in Southwestern Nigeria: evidence from smallholder farming households. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International*, 29(34), 51469–51488. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-19544-w>

Otiono, K. (Kika). (2021). Blood in Biafra: Re-evaluating politics and ethnocultural conflict in the Nigerian-Biafran War. *History Compass*, 19(7). <https://doi.org/10.1111/hic3.12663>

Oyelade, O. (2008). A Critique Of The Rights Of Refugees Under The OAU Convention Governing The Specific Aspects Of Refugee Problems In Africa. *East African Journal of Peace and Human Rights*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.4314/eajphr.v12i2.39349>

Provan, L., & Forrest, E. H. (2023). Alcohol and the liver. *Medicine*, 51(5), 331–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mpmed.2023.02.005>

Razmara, P., Ali, D. W., Zaveri, D., & Thannhauser, M. (2023). Acute effect of delta-9-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) on neuromuscular transmission and locomotive behaviours in larval zebrafish. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 129(4), 833–842. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00438.2022>

Rohde, N., Tang, K. K., Osberg, L., & Rao, P. (2016). The effect of economic insecurity on mental health: Recent evidence from Australian panel data. *Social Science & Medicine*, 151, 250–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2015.12.014>

Sams, C., & Cheng, S. (2023). Atypical Withdrawal Symptoms after Abrupt Tramadol Discontinuation: A Case Report. In *Journal of Pain & Palliative Care Pharmacotherapy* (Vol. 37, Issue 4, pp. 321–323). francis. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15360288.2023.2261913>

Singwane, T., & Ramoshaba, D. (2023). It's like an uncontrollable demon in your body: The lived experiences of youth using crystal meth during the COVID-19 pandemic in Witbank, Mpumalanga. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147- 4478), 12(5), 286–294. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v12i5.2726>

- Soltan, M., Hammad, S., Mohamed, N., El Hamrawy, L., Rajab, A., & El Bahy, M. (2013). Dual diagnosis and psychosocial correlates in substance abuse in Menoufia, Egypt. *Menoufia Medical Journal*, 26(2), 114. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1110-2098.126139>
- Sultan, N., Saher, A., & Noureen, S. (2024). Demographic and Clinical Profile of Persons with Substance Abuse Disorder Attending Happy Life Psychological Services Islamabad, Pakistan. *Journal of Professional & Applied Psychology*, 5(2), 374–383. <https://doi.org/10.52053/jpap.v5i2.177>
- Suvrathan, A., Ghosh, S., Anilkumar, S., Tomar, A., Chattarji, S., & Bennur, S. (2014). Stress enhances fear by forming new synapses with greater capacity for long-term potentiation in the amygdala. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 369(1633), 20130151. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2013.0151>
- Tadayoni, A., Marmur, J., Jean-Louis, F., Mcfarlane, S., Chaudhary, H., Adedayo, A., & Çavuşoğlu, E. (2020). A case series of potential mechanisms of acute coronary syndrome in a marijuana smoker cohort. 17(3), 1478–1481. [https://doi.org/10.37532/2044-9038.2020.17\(3\).418](https://doi.org/10.37532/2044-9038.2020.17(3).418)
- Tar, U. A., & Ayegba, S. B. (2021). Resilience and livelihood strategies among internally displaced persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria (pp. 124–142). . <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003211525-10>
- Tarasuk, V., Cheng, J., Gundersen, C., De Oliveira, C., & Kurdyak, P. (2018). The Relation between Food Insecurity and Mental Health Care Service Utilization in Ontario. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 63(8), 557–569. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0706743717752879>
- Torrens, M., Deruvo, G., Somain, L., Touzeau, D., Fonseca, F., Maremmanni, I., Walcher, S., Green, J., Rossi, P., Martinez-Riera, R., & Martinez-Sanvisens, D. (2014). SY15-3 Prescription Opioids in Southern Europe: Spain. *Alcohol and Alcoholism*, 49(Suppl 1), i15. <https://doi.org/10.1093/alcalc/agu052.66>
- Umukoro, O. L., Taiwo, A., Maroh, I., & Mofoluwake, M. (2016). Prevalence and Patterns of Drug Abuse among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Psychiatry*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.33140/ijp/01/01/00003>
- Umenweke, E.O., Umenweke, O.N. & Onyemaechi, C.I. (2017). Health and Nutrition Lifespan. *Psychologia*, 7 (1).
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2018). Drug use in Nigeria. Available at: https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/statistics/Drugs/Drug_Use_Survey_Nigeria_2019_BOOK.pdf (Accessed September 20, 2024).

Uzor, T. N., Ujuagu, N. A., Offodile, H., N., & Obi, P. A. (2023). Incidence of Drug Abuse -Crystal Methamphetamine among Secondary School Students in Awka Educational Zone, Anambra State. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 7(9), 1933–1940.

Wagner, G., Glick, P., & Khammash, U. (2020). Exposure to violence and its relationship to mental health among young people in Palestine. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, 26(2), 189–197. <https://doi.org/10.26719/2020.26.2.189>

Zaman, T., Knight, J., Malowney, M., & Boyd, J. W. (2015). Co-Occurrence of Substance-Related and Other Mental Health Disorders Among Adolescent Cannabis Users. *Journal of Addiction Medicine*, 9(4), 317–321. <https://doi.org/10.1097/adm.000000000000138>.